

ISic1314

Funerary inscription for Myrtale

Language

Type

Material

Object

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di
Catania, inventory 272

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 31.6 cm

Width 29.4 cm

Depth 1.22 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: 16-22 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not measured mm

Text

Edition: PHI140807

1. Θ (εοῖς) Κ (αταχθονίοις) .
2. Μυρτάλη χρηστο-
3. τάτη, ἔζησεν ἔτη
4. λ, μῆν (ας) γ □ Κορνήλι-
5. ος Ἀγαθήμερος συν-
6. βίω εὐσεβεστάτη □
7. □ ἐποίησε. □

Edition: PHI316232

1. Θ (εοῖς) Κ (αταχθονίοις) ·
2. Μυρτάλη χρηστο-
3. τάτη ἔζησεν ἔτη
4. λ, μῆν (ας) γ· Κορνήλι-
5. ος Ἀγαθήμερος συν-
6. βίω εὐσεβεστάτη □
7. □ ἐποίησε. □

Apparatus

Translation (en)

To the gods of the underworld. Myrtale, most worthy, lived for 30 years, 3 months. Kornelios

Agathemeros made this for his most devoted partner in life.

Translation (it)

Agli dèi del mondo sotterraneo. Myrtale, degnissima, visse 30 anni e 3 mesi. Kornelios Agathemeros lo

ha fatto per la sua devotissima compagna di vita.

Commentary

This epitaph was found together with no.26, which was apparently erected in memory of the same man as set up this text (although it is also possible that they are father and son). The implication is that Myrtale was his first wife and that he remarried (to Euphrosyne) after her death. The differing letter forms and use of Greek numerals indicate that this was engraved by a different stonemason.

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PHI 316232

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. *Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0492 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Korhonen, K. 2004. *Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione.* Helsinki. At 111

Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. *Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum.* Berlin. At 3.5717

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